

Digital Story Time

Year 3 Endline

November 2025

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Acronyms

- **DST:** Digital Story Time
- **KOL:** Kentalis Observation List

Project Overview

Background, Study Design and
Methodology

Background: Overview

The **Digital Story Time** (DST) is a project by eKitabu, funded by **iGravity**, that has been implementing interventions to different schools for the Deaf across Kenya for the last 3 years. The main objective of the project is to create a sign-language rich learning environment for deaf learners in Early Childhood Development (ECD) by providing DST video content, teacher training, and support programs.

At the start, a pilot study was carried out in two units for the deaf in Nairobi - Aga Khan and Racecourse Primary school. While in the first year, 5 schools were included in the study, with 2 being in the control group while 3 being in the treatment group thus receiving the interventions.

In the second year, 5 new schools were included while now for the third year, 24 schools were involved in the study.

Background: Overview

Study Design: Methodology

- This is a quasi experimental study with interventions being implemented in the treatment schools
- In year 1, the Difference in Difference (DiD) design was used to estimate the effect of the intervention by comparing the changes in outcomes over time between the population receiving the intervention (**treatment group**) and the one that was not (**control group**).
- In year 2, the Difference in Difference (DiD) design was not possible since all the schools received the interventions.

Study Design: Intervention Package

The Sign Language Rich Environment Intervention Package

Study Design: Data Collection

- Data is collected from the learners using the **Kentallis Observation List (KOL)** across Pre Primary 1, Pre Primary 2, Grade 1 and Grade 2 at both baseline and endline.
- A **teachers' survey** is also conducted at baseline and endline to understand their experience administering the KOL tools.

Study Design: Data Analysis

- The learners' performances are evaluated through their **learning gains**
- The **learning gains** are the differences between the mean scores at endline and the mean scores at baseline

Metric 1: Reach

Period	Target	Variance	Schools	Learners Reached
Yr 1 - 2023	132	+39	3	171
Yr 2 - 2024	492	+28	10	520
Yr 3 - 2025	852	+187	24	1039

Metric 2: Learning Gains

Period	Minimum	Target	Learning Gains Achieved
Yr 1 - 2023	N/A	N/A	N/A
Yr 2 - 2024	0.16	0.28	0.27
Yr 3 - 2025			0.37

Kentallis Observation List

Demographics, Scores

KOL: Overview

- The Kentallis Observation List tool has 4 different sections;
 - Demographics
 - Communicative conditions
 - Understanding
 - Production
- There is a specific tool for each grade: **Tool 1** (*Pre Primary 1*), **Tool 2** (*Pre Primary 2*), **Tool 3** (*Grade 1*), **Tool 4** (*Grade 2*)
- The learners performance is evaluated across 4 options/ranges for each of the question in the tool: *Below expectations (1)*, *Approaching expectations (2)*, *Meeting expectations (3)*, *Exceeding expectations (4)*

KOL: Overview

A total of **24** schools were part of the year 3 cohort and were as follows:

1. Garissa Special School For The Deaf
2. Hola Primary School For The Deaf
3. Kambui School For The Deaf
4. Kaaga School For The Deaf
5. Kapsabet School For The Deaf
6. Kedowa School For The Deaf
7. Kerugoya School For The Deaf
8. Kibarani School For The Deaf
9. Kitui School For The Deaf
10. Kuja Comprehensive Special School
11. Kwale School For The Deaf
12. Machakos School For The Deaf
13. Maseno School For The Deaf
14. Mundika Primary School For The Deaf
15. Mumias School For The Deaf
16. Ngala School For The Deaf
17. Segla School For The Deaf
18. St.Kizito Litein School for the Deaf
19. Murang'a School for the Deaf
20. Tumutumu School For The Deaf
21. Wajir Primary School For The Deaf
22. St. Antony Special School for the Hearing Impaired
23. Ziwani School For The Deaf
24. St. Luke's School For The Deaf

KOL: Demographics

Count	PP1	PP2	Grade 1	Grade 2	All
Boys	92	137	147	160	536
Girls	119	122	143	119	503
Total	211	259	290	279	1039

Grade 1 has the highest number of learners at 290, while PP1 has the lowest at 211.

Age	PP1	PP2	Grade 1	Grade 2	All
Boys	7.91	8.71	9.60	10.42	9.32
Girls	7.65	8.18	9.68	10.31	8.98
Overall	7.76	8.46	9.64	10.37	9.15

Expectedly, the mean age gradually increases from one grade to the next. Starts at an average age of 7.76 years for PP1 onwards to an average age of 10.37 years for Grade 2.

KOL: PP1 Count

School	Count	School	Count	School	Count
1. Garissa	3	9. Kitui	3	17. Segwa	7
2. Hola	1	10. Kuja	5	18. St.Kizito Litein	12
3. Kambui	21	11. Kwale	3	19. Murang'a	21
4. Kaaga	17	12. Machakos	8	20. Tumutumu	6
5. Kapsabet	2	13. Maseno	5	21. Wajir	6
6. Kedowa	6	14. Mundika	5	22. St. Antony	9
7. Kerugoya	23	15. Mumias	4	23. Ziwani	11
8. Kibarani	5	16. Ngala	18	24. St. Lukes	10

KOL: PP1 Learning Gains

School	Scores	School	Scores	School	Scores
1. Garissa	-0.04	9. Kitui	1.08	17. Segu	0.38
2. Hola	0.12	10. Kuja	0.13	18. St.Kizito Litein	0.28
3. Kambui	0.78	11. Kwale	0.10	19. Murang'a	0.23
4. Kaaga	0.35	12. Machakos	0.59	20. Tumutumu	0.18
5. Kapsabet	0.68	13. Maseno	1.16	21. Wajir	0.04
6. Kedowa	0.73	14. Mundika	0.32	22. St. Antony	0.71
7. Kerugoya	-0.23	15. Mumias	0.47	23. Ziwani	1.53
8. Kibarani	0.14	16. Ngala	-0.20	24. St. Lukes	0.51

KOL: PP2 Count

School	Count	School	Count	School	Count
1. Garissa	6	9. Kitui	8	17. Segwa	4
2. Hola	2	10. Kuja	6	18. St.Kizito Litein	14
3. Kambui	13	11. Kwale	7	19. Murang'a	21
4. Kaaga	18	12. Machakos	20	20. Tumutumu	6
5. Kapsabet	6	13. Maseno	9	21. Wajir	16
6. Kedowa	7	14. Mundika	3	22. St. Antony	9
7. Kerugoya	15	15. Mumias	16	23. Ziwani	10
8. Kibarani	8	16. Ngala	26	24. St. Lukes	9

KOL: PP2 Learning Gains

School	Scores	School	Scores	School	Scores
1. Garissa	1.11	9. Kitui	0.28	17. Segu	1.34
2. Hola	0.57	10. Kuja	0.40	18. St.Kizito Litein	0.28
3. Kambui	0.43	11. Kwale	0.51	19. Murang'a	0.40
4. Kaaga	-0.92	12. Machakos	0.73	20. Tumutumu	1.22
5. Kapsabet	0.24	13. Maseno	-0.11	21. Wajir	0.16
6. Kedowa	0.10	14. Mundika	0.64	22. St. Antony	0.46
7. Kerugoya	0.42	15. Mumias	0.83	23. Ziwani	0.34
8. Kibarani	-0.34	16. Ngala	0.29	24. St. Lukes	0.40

KOL: Grade 1 Count

School	Count	School	Count	School	Count
1. Garissa	12	9. Kitui	3	17. Segwa	6
2. Hola	7	10. Kuja	13	18. St.Kizito Litein	9
3. Kambui	26	11. Kwale	8	19. Murang'a	16
4. Kaaga	13	12. Machakos	15	20. Tumutumu	15
5. Kapsabet	11	13. Maseno	10	21. Wajir	33
6. Kedowa	7	14. Mundika	1	22. St. Antony	8
7. Kerugoya	17	15. Mumias	9	23. Ziwani	16
8. Kibarani	11	16. Ngala	13	24. St. Lukes	11

KOL: Grade 1 Learning Gains

School	Scores	School	Scores	School	Scores
1. Garissa	0.59	9. Kitui	0.09	17. Segu	0.85
2. Hola	0.27	10. Kuja	0.14	18. St.Kizito Litein	0.04
3. Kambui	0.05	11. Kwale	1.27	19. Murang'a	0.35
4. Kaaga	0.42	12. Machakos	0.39	20. Tumutumu	0.92
5. Kapsabet	0.18	13. Maseno	-0.07	21. Wajir	0.66
6. Kedowa	-0.07	14. Mundika	0.06	22. St. Antony	0.81
7. Kerugoya	0.30	15. Mumias	0.10	23. Ziwani	0.69
8. Kibarani	0.93	16. Ngala	0.14	24. St. Lukes	0.43

KOL: Grade 2 Count

School	Count	School	Count	School	Count
1. Garissa	7	9. Kitui	5	17. Segwa	2
2. Hola	5	10. Kuja	9	18. St.Kizito Litein	3
3. Kambui	24	11. Kwale	6	19. Murang'a	16
4. Kaaga	24	12. Machakos	13	20. Tumutumu	10
5. Kapsabet	5	13. Maseno	13	21. Wajir	15
6. Kedowa	10	14. Mundika	4	22. St. Antony	16
7. Kerugoya	15	15. Mumias	9	23. Ziwani	13
8. Kibarani	29	16. Ngala	12	24. St. Lukes	14

KOL: Grade 2 Learning Gains

School	Scores	School	Scores	School	Scores
1. Garissa	0.72	9. Kitui	-0.08	17. Segu	0.04
2. Hola	-0.11	10. Kuja	-0.01	18. St.Kizito Litein	0.71
3. Kambui	0.25	11. Kwale	1.46	19. Murang'a	0.21
4. Kaaga	0	12. Machakos	-0.03	20. Tumutumu	0.71
5. Kapsabet	0.12	13. Maseno	0.44	21. Wajir	0.69
6. Kedowa	0.21	14. Mundika	0.37	22. St. Antony	0.56
7. Kerugoya	0.30	15. Mumias	0.61	23. Ziwani	0.15
8. Kibarani	0.77	16. Ngala	0.17	24. St. Lukes	0.26

KOL: Overall Count

School	Count	School	Count	School	Count
1. Garissa	28	9. Kitui	19	17. Segu	19
2. Hola	15	10. Kuja	33	18. St.Kizito Litein	38
3. Kambui	84	11. Kwale	24	19. Murang'a	74
4. Kaaga	72	12. Machakos	56	20. Tumutumu	37
5. Kapsabet	24	13. Maseno	37	21. Wajir	70
6. Kedowa	30	14. Mundika	13	22. St. Antony	42
7. Kerugoya	70	15. Mumias	38	23. Ziwani	50
8. Kibarani	53	16. Ngala	69	24. St. Lukes	44

KOL: Overall Learning Gains

School	Scores	School	Scores	School	Scores
1. Garissa	0.67	9. Kitui	0.28	17. Segu	0.69
2. Hola	0.17	10. Kuja	0.14	18. St.Kizito Litein	0.26
3. Kambui	0.35	11. Kwale	0.95	19. Murang'a	0.30
4. Kaaga	-0.07	12. Machakos	0.44	20. Tumutumu	0.79
5. Kapsabet	0.22	13. Maseno	0.27	21. Wajir	0.50
6. Kedowa	0.22	14. Mundika	0.39	22. St. Antony	0.62
7. Kerugoya	0.15	15. Mumias	0.57	23. Ziwani	0.66
8. Kibarani	0.58	16. Ngala	0.11	24. St. Lukes	0.31

Learning Gains: Summary

- Average learning gains across the sample: **0.37**
- Average learning gains across PP1: 0.36
- Average learning gains across PP2: 0.33
- Average learning gains across Grade 1: 0.42
- Average learning gains across Grade 2: 0.36